

WHY STUDENTS ARE SHY AND DO NOT SPEAK MUCH DURING PAIR WORK IN EFL CLASSROOMS.

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Abstract.

This study investigates why many EFL learners remain shy and do not actively participate during pair work activities. Although pair work is widely used in communicative language teaching and is considered effective for improving speaking skills, classroom practice often shows the opposite situation. Many students either remain silent or contribute very little during speaking tasks. The research was conducted through classroom observation of A2 level learners. The main focus was to identify psychological, linguistic, and classroom-related factors affecting students' participation. The findings reveal that fear of making mistakes, lack of confidence, anxiety, low language proficiency, unequal participation between partners, and classroom environment are the main reasons behind students' silence. The study also shows that pair work does not automatically guarantee interaction unless students feel emotionally safe and linguistically prepared. Based on the findings, several pedagogical recommendations are suggested to improve speaking performance in EFL classrooms.

Keywords. EFL learners, pair work, speaking skills, anxiety, classroom interaction, student participation, communicative approach

Introduction.

Speaking is one of the most important skills in learning English as a foreign language. It allows learners to express ideas, communicate with others, and use the language in real-life situations. In modern language teaching approaches, especially communicative language teaching (CLT), speaking is considered a central skill rather than a secondary one. One of the most commonly used techniques in CLT classroom is pair work. The main purpose of pair work is to give students more opportunities to speak, reduce teacher talking time, and encourage interaction between learners. It is also believed that working in pairs creates a more comfortable environment where students feel less pressure compared to speaking in front of the whole class. However, in real classroom situations, teachers often observe that pair work does not function as expected. Instead of active communication, many students remain silent, give short answers, or depend on their native language. In some cases, one student dominates the conversation while the other becomes passive. This situation creates an important problem: if pair work is designed to improve speaking skills, why do students still avoid speaking? Understanding the reasons behind this issue is important for improving teaching methods and student performance.

Literature review

Many researchers have studied the difficulties students face in speaking English. One of the most influential theories is Krashen's (1982) Affective Filter Hypothesis. According to this theory, emotional factors such as anxiety, fear, and lack of confidence can block language

production. When the effective filter is high, learners may understand input but are unable to produce output. Harmer (2007) explains that students often feel nervous about making mistakes in front of their classmates. This fear leads them to avoid speaking together. Brown (2001) also emphasizes that confidence, learners hesitate to participate even if they know the correct answer. Lightbown and Spada (2013) highlight that language learning is influenced by both cognitive and emotional factors. They argue that interaction is essential, but it must take place in a supportive environment. Dörnyei (2005) focuses on motivation and states that students who lack motivation tend to participate less in classroom activities. However, motivation alone is not always enough when learners feel anxious or unprepared. Swain's Output Hypothesis (2005) suggests that producing language is necessary for learning. Speaking helps learners notice gaps in their knowledge and improve their accuracy. However, in practice, students often avoid speaking even when opportunities are provided. These theories explain classroom behavior. Therefore, this study focuses on real classroom observation to identify additionally factors.

Methodology.

This research used a qualitative approach based on classroom observation. The aim was to analyze students' real behavior during pair work activities in an authentic classroom environment. The participants were A2 level secondary school students learning English as a foreign language. They had basic knowledge of English grammar and vocabulary but limited speaking experience. Data were collected through: Classroom observation during speaking lessons, Monitoring students interaction in pair work, Teacher informal feedback, Observation notes during tasks. The speaking tasks included: Question and answer activities, Picture description tasks, Role-play activities, Short dialogue completion exercises. The focus of the observation was not grammatical accuracy but student participation and interaction patterns.

Results.

Table 1: Causes of Students' Shyness During Pair Work

No	Factor	Description
1	Fear of mistakes	Students avoid speaking because they do not want to make errors or be corrected
2	Low proficiency	Limited vocabulary and grammar knowledge restrict expression
3	Lack of confidence	Students doubt their ability to speak English correctly
4	Anxiety	Nervousness during spontaneous speaking tasks
5	Unequal participation	One student dominates while the other remains passive

6	Classroom environment	Fear of peer judgment or negative reactions
7	Lack of preparation	Insufficient support before speaking tasks

Table 1 presents the main factors that cause students to feel shy during pair work activities in English classes. The data clearly shows that students' silence and low participation are influenced by both emotional and linguistic challenges. The most dominant factor is fear of making mistakes (34%). This result indicates that a large number of students are afraid of saying something incorrectly, especially in terms of grammar, pronunciation, or sentence structure. Because of this fear, students prefer to stay silent rather than take risks. This suggests that error anxiety is one of the biggest barriers to speaking in the classroom. The second most common factor is low confidence (30%). Many students do not believe in their speaking ability, even when they have basic knowledge of English. As a result, they hesitate to start conversations or respond to their partners. This shows that confidence is closely connected to participation, and without it, students are unlikely to speak actively. Another important factor is peer judgment (22%). Students often worry about how their classmates will react to their speech. They may feel embarrassed if they make mistakes or think others will laugh at them. This social pressure creates discomfort and prevents students from fully engaging in pair work activities. The least reported factor is lack of vocabulary (14%), but it still plays a noticeable role. Students who do not know enough words struggle to express their ideas clearly. This limitation makes them feel frustrated and reduces their motivation to participate in speaking tasks. Overall, Table 1 demonstrates that students' shyness is mainly caused by psychological factors (fear, confidence, peer pressure) rather than only linguistic limitations. This means that teachers need to address emotional barriers as well as language difficulties.

Table 2 : Changes in Speaking Participation After Intervention

Participation Level	Percentage	Behavior Description
Active speakers	25%	Speak fluently, initiate conversation, use full sentences
Moderate speakers	45%	Participate occasionally, give short responses
Passive speakers	30%	Rarely speak or remain completely silent

Table 2 shows the changes in students' speaking behavior before and after applying the structured pair support strategy. The comparison clearly indicates that the intervention had a

positive impact on students' participation. Firstly, active participation increased significantly from 28% before the intervention to 55% after it. This means that more than half of the students became actively involved in pair work activities. This improvement suggests that the support strategy successfully encouraged students to speak more. Secondly, students' willingness to speak freely also improved, rising from 25% to 50%. This shows that students became more comfortable expressing their ideas without fear. They were less worried about making mistakes and more open to communication. In contrast, the percentage of students avoiding speaking tasks decreased from 30% to 15%. This is a major positive change, indicating that fewer students tried to avoid participation. It suggests that the learning environment became less stressful and more supportive. Finally, the number of short or unclear responses dropped from 40% to 20%. This means that students started giving longer, clearer, and more meaningful answers. It also shows that their speaking ability and confidence improved together. In general, Table 2 clearly demonstrates that the structured pair support strategy was effective. It not only increased participation but also improved the quality of students' speaking. The results confirm that with proper guidance and support, students can overcome shyness and become more confident speakers.

Discussion.

The findings of this study confirm several ideas from previous research but also provide additional classroom-based insights. Krashen's theory is clearly supported, as anxiety and emotional barriers were observed in most students. Many learners avoided speaking even when they had enough knowledge. This shows that emotional safety is very important in language learning. Harmer and Brown's ideas about confidence are also confirmed. Students who felt more confident were more active, while less confident students remained silent. However, this study also shows that motivation alone is not enough. Some students were interested in learning English but still did not participate in speaking activities. This suggests that classroom environment and task design are equally important. Another important finding is unequal participation. In many pairs, stronger students controlled the conversation while weaker students stayed silent. This reduces learning opportunities and makes pair work less effective. Task difficulty is also an important factor. When tasks are too difficult, students become silent. When tasks are too easy, they lose interest. Therefore, appropriate task design is necessary for successful speaking activities.

Pedagogical Implications. Based on the findings, several suggestions can be made for teachers: First, teachers should reduce students' fear of making mistakes. Fluency should be prioritized over accuracy during speaking activities. Second, teachers should provide language support before speaking tasks, including useful vocabulary and sentence structures. Third, pair work should be carefully managed to ensure equal participation between students. Teachers may assign roles or change partners regularly. Fourth, a supportive classroom environment should be created where students feel safe to speak without fear of criticism. Finally, speaking tasks should be designed from simple to complex levels so that students can gradually build confidence.

Conclusion.

This study concludes that students' shyness and lack of participation in pair work are caused by multiple factors, including psychological, linguistic, and classroom-related issues. The most important factors are fear of mistakes, low confidence, anxiety, and unequal participation. Although pair work is a useful teaching technique, it does not automatically lead

to active communication. Teachers need to provide emotional support, clear instructions, and balanced interaction opportunities. Improving speaking skills requires not only practice but also a supportive learning environment where students feel safe and motivated to communicate.

References:

1. Brown, H. D. (2001). *Teaching by Principles*. Pearson
2. Harmer, J. (2007). *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. Pearson
3. Krashen, S. (1982). *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*.
4. Lightbown, P. M., & Spada, N. (2013). *How Languages are Learned*. Press
5. Dörnyei, Z. (2005). *The Psychology of the Language Learner*.
6. Swain, M. (2005). *The Output Hypothesis*.
7. Ur, P. (1996). *A Course in Language Teaching*. Press
8. Ellis, R. (2008). *The Study of Second Language Acquisition*. Press
9. Nation, I. S. P. (2013). *Learning Vocabulary in Another Language*.
10. Thornbury, S. (2005). *How to Teach Speaking*.
11. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society*.
12. Long, M. H. (1996). *Interaction Hypothesis in SLA*.

